

**SOCIAL ADAPTATION OF THE POPULATION EVACUATED TO
UZBEKISTAN (1941-1945)**

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Аннотация: В данной статье говорится о социальной адаптации населения, эвакуированного в Узбекистан в годы Второй мировой войны и в этот период.

Ключевые слова: Вторая мировая война, социальное положение Узбекистана, эвакуация, социальная адаптация населения, глобальные риски.

Abstract: This article talks about the social adaptation of the population evacuated to Uzbekistan during the Second World War and that period.

Keywords: the Second World War, the social situation of Uzbekistan, evacuation, social adaptation of the population, global risks.

In today's era, when global threats are increasing in the world and the realization of national identity and the recovery of our true history are becoming more important than ever, the state and public figures, science, culture, and art, literature, are brutally repressed by the authoritarian regime. It remains an urgent task to perpetuate the names and memories of thousands of our compatriots who have a simple profession, to educate the young generation in the spirit of love and loyalty to the Motherland and the people, following the example of their courage and perseverance. After all, "National history should be created with a national spirit. Otherwise, it will not have an educational effect. We need to teach our

youth to learn from history, to draw conclusions, to arm them with the science of history and historical thinking" [2].

In 1941-1945, it had a serious impact on the relations of the population evacuated to Uzbekistan with society. During the Second World War, the inhabitants of the western regions of the Soviet Union were forced to leave their homes due to the German attack and were evacuated to the Central Asian republics, in particular to Uzbekistan. During this evacuation, there was interaction between the evacuees and the native population in Uzbekistan. With the arrival of foreigners, there were differences in the customs, culture, and lifestyle of the local people. However, in general, the evacuees were warmly welcomed and supported by the local population. In the process of evacuation, the solidarity and tolerance of society came to the fore in Uzbekistan. Displaced people were provided with shelter, food, and other necessities, and solidarity was shown with them. As a result, the relations of the population evacuated to Uzbekistan in 1941-1945 with society reflect the period when an approach based on solidarity and tolerance was adopted. This process emphasized the ability of different communities to live together and support each other.

The First World War brought great changes and trials to many countries, including Uzbekistan, which became a refuge for many evacuees. The social adaptation of the population evacuated to Uzbekistan during the First World War was a complex process that required the joint efforts of both the evacuees and the local population.

Evacuees who came to Uzbekistan as a result of the war faced several difficulties, such as language barriers, unusual climates, and cultural differences. They were often left without housing, work, and means of living. The local population also faced problems with the need to help and support the newcomers.

However, thanks to the efforts of the government, public organizations, and volunteers, the evacuees gradually began to adapt to the new conditions. A

temporary shelter was established, food and medical assistance were provided, training and employment were provided. Over time, many evacuees found their place in Uzbek society, united, and became active participants in various spheres of life. Their experience and knowledge contributed to cultural exchange and diversity in Uzbekistan.

Thus, although the social adaptation of the population evacuated to Uzbekistan during the First World War was a complex process, thanks to the efforts of all parties, people were able to overcome difficulties and find their place in new conditions.

The social integration of the population evacuated to Uzbekistan during the First World War was a process that required mutual efforts and cooperation between the evacuees and the local population. During the war, people who left their homes and sought refuge in Uzbekistan had to adapt to a new environment and start a new life. Evacuees faced challenges such as language barriers, cultural differences, and unfamiliar climatic conditions. Although they faced problems with housing, employment, and livelihood, they had to make efforts to communicate and integrate with the local population.

On the other hand, a helping hand was extended to the evacuated population due to the help and assistance provided by the Government of Uzbekistan, NGOs, and volunteers. Temporary shelter was provided, food and medical aid organizations were established, and education and employment were provided. Over time, the evacuated people joined the society of Uzbekistan, adapted to a new life, and became an active part of the society. In this process, both the experiences of the evacuees and the support of the local population facilitated the process of social adaptation and it was completed.

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